

Influence of the Family Structure on Emotional Intelligence

Divya

Ph.D Scholar, Department of Education, Faculty of Education, S.V.S.U. (Meerut U.P.)
250005, Email:- dvybghl@gmail.com

Dr. Indira Singh

Prof. & Head, Department of Education, Faculty of Education, S.V.S.U. (Meerut U.P.),
250005, Email:- indirasingh285@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18871905>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 16-02-2026

Published: 10-03-2026

Keywords:

*emotional intelligence,
households, family,
emotions*

ABSTRACT

As society is evolving with each passing day, keeping up with its pace has become an integral part of life. As nowadays emotional intelligence is getting priority amongst other characteristics, it has become an inevitable part of an individual personality to become successful and satisfied in their life. Emotional intelligence is developed during the early days of life and family and schooling play an important role in the same. Consequently, the purpose of this study is to find out the influence of family structure on emotional intelligence. As the most prominent family structures of India are a joint family and nuclear family, the same is being considered in the study. The study also draws out a comparison between the emotional intelligence of students from the joint family to find out if it varies. A sample size of 100 students of the IX standard has been taken from five private schools in Delhi. The sample size also includes 20 parents of IX standard students. The sample size was selected by a random probability sampling method. The data was collected through the survey method. The tools for data collection include Open-ended questionnaires and unstructured interviews developed by the researcher; and Emotional Intelligence Scale by A. K. Singh and Shruti Narain. The study shows that most of

the parents and other family members; belonging to joint family and nuclear families; pay attention to their child's emotions and inculcate emotional intelligence. They make them aware of their emotions and help in managing emotions, motivating themselves, recognizing emotions in others as well as in handling their relationship with others, whereas a few parents and family members are ignorant. The results also revealed that emotional intelligence does not vary with the different types of family structure students belong to. Students from a joint family as well as the nuclear family have the almost same level of emotional intelligence. These findings are consistent with the findings of the study analyzing the Emotional Intelligence of College Students among Joint and Nuclear Families which shows that there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence among joint and nuclear families (Fidha & Haris, 2018). Whereas, these findings are contradictory to the study investigating the dynamics of Family Structure on the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary 2 School children which states that students from joint families are much more emotionally stronger than the students from the nuclear family. (Ravindran, 2020)

1 Introduction

Family plays a vital role in the development of the child. It is the preliminary experience of society for the child and they learn to behave in a social set up. It is the environment where children learn to use their faculties and learn how family relationships work. Family relationship develops a sense of belongingness amongst individuals. It provides individual with love, care, support and enable them to gain knowledge and life time values. Family can be defined as a group of people related by blood, marriage or adaption and, when live together, form an economic unit and bear and raise children. (Benokraitis, 1996). Family research provides insight into the structure of society and the changes taking place in the types, composition, and rowth of families (Hodgson & Birks, 2002). Families can be classified in several different dimensions, for example, by marriage type (monogamous, polygamous), by location (patrilocal, matrilocal, and avunculocal), authority (patriarchy, matriarchy), and by kin composition (nuclear, joint) (UNESCO, 1992). According to Census of India (Ministry of Home Affairs,

1991), Indian families comprise largely of nuclear family structure with joint families forming about a fifth of the total households (Census of India, 1981). In general, the Nuclear family consists of parents and their children who stay together. Whereas in a joint family a married couple lives with their children, married children, grandchildren. Sometimes close relatives of the male lineage also stay in the joint family. In this family structure, more than one lineage stays together as one family. A joint family is the extension of the nuclear family. Emotions are greatly influenced by the individuals of the family. Parents play the role of torch bearer when it comes to the behavioural, emotional, physical and psychological development of an individual. Studies have given a significant value to parenting in influencing a child's emotional growth. Studies have further found that parent's beliefs, responses and attitudes towards their offspring's emotional expressions have an influence on their offspring's emotional abilities (Gottman,1997). Intelligence have been an intriguing area of research due to its complexity and unpredictability. Initially is was perceived from cognitive aspect until the Thorndike's social intelligence and 3 Gardner's multiple intelligence theories came into existence. Such theories led to the broadening of the perspectives to intelligence. The term Emotional Intelligence was first used and defined by Peter Salovy and John Mayer as: "A form of intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions". Later, Daniel Goleman and Bar-On gave their definitions and model of emotional intelligence. To Daniel Goleman, means managing feelings so that they are expressed appropriately and affectively, enabling people to work together smoothly toward their common goal. Emotional intelligence is the new yardstick which is applied to assess a person's well-being in life. Emotional intelligence is a vastly researched area due to its ambiguity and its prevalent use in the currently evolving society. Researchers have found contradicting results for the relationship between the emotional intelligence of the individuals belonging to different family structures. The study analysing the Emotional Intelligence of College Students among Joint and Nuclear Families shows that there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence among joint and nuclear families (Fidha & Haris, 2018). The study investigating the dynamics of Family Structure on the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School children states that students from join family are much more emotionally stronger than the students from the nuclear family. (Ravindran, 2020)

This paper will try to explain this points:

- 1: How does family as a structure influence the Emotional Intelligence of students?
- 2: What features of a family do influence the low and high Emotional Intelligence of students?

3: What are the issues and their types that are discussed by the students with their family members?

4: How does family as a unit respond to the issues of the students?

5: How does Emotional Intelligence vary with family structure?

2 Conceptual Framework

2.1 Family Structure

Family structure is the hierarchy of individuals belonging to the same paternal background. Family structures are of different types namely, Nuclear Family, Joint Family or Extended Family, Single Parent Family, Childless Family, Step Family, Grandparent Family and so on. But in this study we will consider the most common family structure types in India, i.e., Nuclear Family and Joint family.

2.2 Types of family structure

2.2.1 Joint Family

Joint families are families with two or more adults who are linked through blood or marriage, usually along with children. A joint family live together for social support and to achieve common goals. For example, parents, their children, and their children's grandparents live together. This provides the family with the ability to provide care for their elderly, and in turn, the grandparents can also help with childcare while the parents are at work.

Joint families are close and they give each other a lot of support. Although it is not easy for so many family members to live together. Differences in opinion may arise in joint families, and some people might live this way because they are obligated against their wishes.

2.2.2 Nuclear Family

The nuclear family is also known as elementary or traditional families, consists of two parents and their children. Nuclear families may have one or more children who are biological or adopted, but the main idea is that the parents are rearing their kids together in the family home.

Nuclear families can be strong and successful, as both parents set a great example for their kids. These kids often have several advantages over other families with less, which can help them get ahead in life. However, like any family, nuclear families may face difficulties. For example, if parents shut out

grandparents and other family members, they are more likely to lose their support system, and thus getting through hard times can be challenging.

2.3 Emotions

Emotion is a complicated psychological phenomenon which takes place as animals or people live their lives. Emotions involve physiological motivation, appraisal of the situation, expressive behaviours, and conscious experience. Emotion is related to feeling, mood, temperament, personality, disposition, and motivation. Emotion is a complicated experience of consciousness, bodily sensation, and behaviour that shows the personal importance of a thing, an event, or a state of affairs.

2.4 Intelligence

Intelligence can be defined as general cognitive problem-solving skills. It is a hypothetical idea which we have defined as being reflected by certain types of behaviour which is observed when we face entirely new situation and don't know exactly what to do. It is a mental capability which is involved in reasoning, perceiving relationships and analogies, calculating, learning quickly... etc. Earlier it was considered that there was one underlying general factor at the intelligence base (the g-factor), but later psychologists sustained that it is more complicated and could not be determined by such a simplistic method. Some psychologists divided intelligence into subcategories. For example Howard Gardner maintained that it contains seven components: musical, bodily-kinesthetic, logical-mathematical, linguistic, spatial, interpersonal, and intrapersonal.

2.5 Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to identify and manage one's own emotions, and others' emotions as well. Emotional intelligence include three skills: emotional awareness, or the ability to identify one's own emotions; the ability to harness those emotions and use them to tasks like thinking and problem solving; and the ability to manage emotions, including both, regulating one's own emotions in necessary situation and helping others to do the same. No validated psychometric test or scale is available for emotional intelligence as there is for "g," the general intelligence factor—and many argue that emotional intelligence is thus not an actual construct, but it is a way of describing interpersonal skills that is identified with other names. Emotional intelligence can be simply defined as the intelligent use of emotions:

Emotional Intelligence can further be described as:

1. Self awareness
2. Managing emotions. .
3. Motivating oneself.
4. Recognizing emotions in others
5. Handling relationships

3 Methodology

The present study lies in the domain of descriptive and is qualitative and quantitative in nature. This study intends to find the influence of family structure on the emotional intelligence of 9 Secondary School Students of Delhi. This study also draws out the comparison between the emotional intelligence of secondary school students belonging to joint family and nuclear family. The data has been collected by using survey method. A sample size of 100 students of IX standard has been taken from five private schools of Delhi. The sample size also includes 20 parents of IX standard from five schools of Delhi (1/4th of each class). The sample size was selected by random probability sampling method. For data collection, the three tools chosen for the present study were open ended questionnaire for students, structured interview for parents and standardised Tool (Emotional Intelligence Scale by A. K. Singh and Shruti Narain). The investigator administered the Emotional Intelligence Scale and open ended questionnaire on IX standard students. The interview was administered on the parents of IX standard students. Data was collected on the basis of responses given by students in the test and the open-ended questionnaire. The data was also collected on the basis of responses given by parents on the structured interview. While taking interviews the investigator ensured that participants feel comfortable and do not hesitate to give answers to the questions. The investigator analysed responses of every question and gave interpretation keeping in mind what had been observed during the interview. In the third tool i.e., Emotional Intelligence Scale Ttest analysis was used compare the emotional intelligence of students from joint family and nuclear family.

4 Literature Review

The influence of family on the emotional intelligence of individual is highly researched area. This might be due to the increasing indulgence and exploration of intelligence in various fields. If we broadly classify the studies into two groups then we can identify the contradictory trends in the researches being done. Some of the studies states that the different aspects of the family or family structures does have a

influence on the emotional intelligence of the individuals; whereas the other studies show that the different aspects of family or family structure do not have a significant relationship with emotional intelligence of the individuals. The studies that show influence of family structure on emotional intelligence have been found to show relationship of family climate to a high-performance level of strategic emotional intelligence. Also, there is a relationship between the various aspects of emotional intelligence with the adolescent's family climate, except interpersonal efficacy. EI level is significantly related to some family factors: psychological climate in the family, strength of subject relations with their mother/ father, subjective perception of family financial status, etc. Parental modelling, encouragement, facilitation, and rewarding has a substantial effect on the students' emotional intelligence. Family environment cultivates emotional intelligence in their early adolescents. The family environment had the most effect on the adolescents' perception and management of emotions that others were feelings. To ensure increase in the unity within the family environment it is important that the families understand themselves, the emotions of the others and guide their emotions. The family relationship influences emotional intelligence of the adolescents. Healthy family relationships do affect positively the emotional intelligence of adolescents. There is an indirect association between family functioning and life satisfaction through the mediating role of emotional intelligence. Furthermore, there is a positive relationship between family functioning and emotional intelligence. The type of family structure to which an adolescent belongs plays an important role in the social and emotional development of the individual. The individuals raised in dual parent households had significantly higher EI than those raised in single parent households. The students from joint family are much more emotionally stronger than the students from the nuclear family. The complexity in environment is experienced by children belonging to large family helps in developing various emotional competencies thus developing higher emotional intelligence. On the contrary some studies show that there is no significant relationship between family or family structure and emotional intelligence of individuals. Family structure does not influence emotional intelligence. There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence among joint and nuclear families, genders, residential areas. Also, there is no relationship between emotional intelligence and number of sibling but there is a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and family size.

5 Discussion

Family structure as a support system in developing emotional intelligence among Secondary School students

Joint families as well as nuclear families try to solve the problems of the children and advise them. Joint families as well as nuclear families encourage the children to discuss their problems with them. Children talk to their mother when they face problems in their academics. Joint families are flexible towards the mistakes the children commit, whereas nuclear families are not flexible towards the mistakes the children commit. Joint families respond aggressively towards the mistakes of the children, whereas nuclear family try to understand their child when they commit a mistake. Also, they explain their children the consequences of such mistakes. Joint families as well as nuclear families interact regularly with the peers of their children. Joint families as well as nuclear families interact regularly with the teacher of their children. Children belonging to joint family and nuclear family feel free to express themselves with their family members. Joint families as well as nuclear families indulge in relaxing activities with their children when the experience exam stress. Also, nuclear families do not get tensed when their child deal with exam stress. Joint families respond aggressively towards the disputes of their child with their siblings/peers. Children belonging to nuclear families do not share the disputes they have amongst their siblings/peers and solve on their own. Joint families as well as nuclear families motivate and help to improve in academics when the child scores low in exams. Joint families respond aggressively towards the misconduct in the child's behaviour, whereas nuclear family try to calm their child whenever they misbehave and explain that their behaviour is not right. Children belonging to joint family interact regularly with their parent, whereas the children belonging to nuclear family interact rarely with their grandparents. Children belonging to joint family and nuclear family interact about themselves with their grandparents. Grandparents belonging to joint family and nuclear family like to talk about their memories and teach their grandchildren moral values. Grandparents belonging to joint family consider teaching moral values to their grandchildren as important. Children belonging to joint family and nuclear family enjoy talking and spending time with their uncle and aunt. Children belonging to joint family likes to share about their day/life with their uncle and aunt, whereas the children belonging to nuclear family don't talk/don't have uncle and aunt. Children belonging to joint family and nuclear family like sharing things/secrets with their cousins. Children belonging to joint family respond aggressively when their cousins fight with them, whereas the children belonging to nuclear family do not fight with their cousins. Children belonging to joint family and nuclear family discuss issues related to their academic life with their family members.

Parents as an agent of family structure to inculcate Emotional

Intelligence among Secondary School Students

Parents like to share a flexible and lenient relationship with their children. Parents belonging to the nuclear family share a mixed kind of relationship. For some issues, they behave leniently whereas for some they prefer being strict with the children. Parents help their children to solve the problem faced by them. Parents of nuclear families motivate their children to solve their problems on their own as they feel their children are mature enough to deal with their problems. Parents help their child to resolve the issues that their change have with their siblings/peers. Parents try to eliminate any negative emotions that they notice in their child's behaviour by getting involved in a conversation with them. Parents try to analyse the influence of the stress on the child and try to eliminate it by motivating them. Parents belonging to joint family indulge in some soothing activities to uplift their child's mood. Parents show aggressive behaviour towards their children when they lie or hide something from them. Parents belonging to joint family, try to talk to their children politely whenever they feel that their child hide something. Parents scold their children to make them withdraw the misconduct in their behaviour. Parents motivate their child to cope up with criticism and failure by helping them to face it.

The effect of family structure on the Emotional Intelligence of

Secondary School students

Secondary School students have average emotional intelligence irrespective of the type of family structure they belong to, i.e. joint family or nuclear family. Approximately half of the students have average emotional intelligence; one third has low emotional intelligence and only one-sixth have high emotional intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School students belonging to the joint family and the nuclear family.

There is no relationship between the type of family structure of secondary school students and their emotional intelligence. Both family structure works in the same manner when it comes to developing emotional intelligence among children. So, there is no comparison between the joint family and nuclear family based on emotional intelligence.

6 Implications

Taking into consideration the findings , the following implications are suggested :

6.3.1 For Students

- Students should be aware of their emotional intelligence. This will help them to develop it and identify their problems.
- Students should try to share their psychological, physical, and emotional problems with their teacher or parents. This will help children to avoid any negative experience.
- Students should indulge with their parents and family members in various life activities and conversations.

6.3.2 For Parents

- Parents should be supportive and understanding of their children.
- Parents should provide children with an environment that enables the children to explore, express, and improve their emotional intelligence.
- Parents should be aware of the emotional intelligence of their children so that they can understand it and work on it accordingly. This will enable the parents to manipulate their children's emotional intelligence according to their needs, thereby improving relationships of their child at school and home.
- Parents should indulge with their children in various life activities and conversations.

6.3.3 For Teacher/ School

- The teacher should provide students with an environment that enables the student to explore, express, and improve their emotional intelligence.
- The teacher should know about the emotional intelligence of the students of her class. This will enable the teacher to identify the emotional problems that hinder their academics and provide ways to deal with it.
- The school should provide counselling for improving the emotional intelligence of students. This will help the students to deal with academic stress, personal problems, and emotional issues, thereby improving their performance and adjustment at school.
- The school should provide counselling for improving emotional intelligence of parents. This will help the parents to understand, express, and guide their children's emotions. This will result in a better understanding amongst the family members and thereby creating a harmonious environment for the development of emotional intelligence amongst children.

- The school should organize seminars and workshops regarding emotional intelligence development that involve the participation of the students with their parents. This will enable the development of understanding and emotional support among them.
- The textbooks should include exercises or activities that encourage the students in exploring their emotional aspects and provide suggestions to improve it. This will help the students to understand their emotional intelligence and be aware of it.

CONCLUSION

The present study aims to find out the influence of family structure on the emotional intelligence of secondary school students. It examines family structure as the support system in developing emotional intelligence amongst children and how parents act as the agent of family structure to inculcate emotional intelligence. It provides insights into the issues that children share with those parents, the way the family handles and reacts towards the mistake children commit, etc. It draws out the comparison between the joint family and nuclear family when it comes to the emotional intelligence of children. It intends to find out the level of emotional intelligence of the children of joint family and nuclear family, to find out trends if any. The study shows that the family indulges in problem-solving in issues related to academic life, personal life, and relationship with others of the children. The family tries to mould the child's behaviour through their reactions. Family support, motivate, and help children in dealing with the emotions they face in their life. It also gives insights into how the children interact emotionally with the different family members and how these interactions differ on the basis of family structure. Parent plays the most important role in emotional intelligence development. Parents keen on their child's emotional state and regularly indulge in discussions or combined activities to analyse their child's emotional state. They keep a close check on them and support them emotionally, support them, guide them, and sometimes scold them when necessary. Also, they help their child in problem-solving and building healthy relationships with others. It is evident from the study that the family influences the emotional aspect of the children. But the emotional intelligence of the children does not vary with the type of family structure the children belong to. The children belonging to joint family and nuclear family have an almost similar level of emotional intelligence. No significant difference was found between the emotional intelligence of children belonging to a joint family and nuclear family. These findings are consistent with the findings of the study analysing the Emotional Intelligence of College Students among Joint and Nuclear Families which shows that there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence among joint and nuclear families (Fidha & Haris, Whereas, these findings are contradictory to the study

investigating the dynamics of Family Structure on the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School children which states that students from joint families are much more emotionally stronger than the students from the nuclear family. (Ravindran, 2020)

References

- Afzal, M. T., & Afzal, M. (2016). Relationship of Family Structure and Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School Students in Islamabad. *American Journal of Educational Research*.
- Alavi, Masoumeh & Mehrinezhad, Seyed & Amini, Mansour & Kaur, Minder. (2017). Family functioning and trait emotional intelligence among youth. *Health Psychology Open*. 4. 205510291774846. 10.1177/2055102917748461.
- Bangkok, Thailand: UNESCO; 1992. UNESCO Principal Regional Office for Asia and Pacific. The changing family in Asia: Bangladesh, India, Japan, Philippines and Thailand. [Google Scholar]
- Bar-On, Reuven. (2012). Emotional and social intelligence: Insights from the Emotional Quotient Inventory..
- Barbar, K.L., Christensen, M.M., & Barchard, K.A. (2004). *Relating Family Size and Birth order to Emotional Intelligence*, UK; Western Psychological Association.
- Benokraitis., N. V. (1996). *Marriages and Families, Changes, Choices &Constraint*:Printice Hall New Jersey.
- Bhatia,G.(2012).A study of Family relationship in relation to emotional intelligence of the students of secondary level *.International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*.
- Burgess, E. W., Lock, H. J. (1916). *The Family from Institution to Companionship*:New York, The American Book Company.
- Chakravarty, Nandini. (2009). Trait Emotional intelligence of the Adolescent: the Relationship with Family Environment.
- Chandran, A. & Nair, B.P.. (2015). Family climate as a predictor of emotional intelligence in adolescents. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*. 41. 167-173.
- Daniel, G. (1996) *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*.London, Great Britain: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc

- Fidha, Ayisha & Haris, Farah. (2018). Emotional Intelligence of College Students among Joint and Nuclear Families. *International Journal of Academic Research and Development*.
- Ghanawat, G.M. & Muke, S.S. & Chaudhury, Suprakash & Kiran, M.. (2016). Relationship of family functioning and emotional intelligence in adolescents. *Pravara Medical Review*. 8. 10-14.
- Gottman, J. M., Katz, L.F., &Hooven, C. (1997). *Meta-emotion: How families communicate emotionally*. Psychology Press.
- G., Ravindran. (2020). Dynamics of Family Structure on Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School Children. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. 24. 1828-1834. 10.37200/IJPR/V24I5/PR201855.
- Hodgson RM, Birks KS. Palmerston North, New Zealand: The Centre for Public Policy Evaluation, Massey University; 2002. Statistics New Zealand's definition of family, its implications for the accuracy of data and effectiveness of policy targeting. Student paper no. 4. [Google Scholar]
- Kaur, R and Jaswal, S. (2005). Relationship Between Strategic Emotional Intelligence and Family Climate of Punjabi Adolescents. *Anthropologist*.
- Lekavičienė, Rosita & Antiniene, Dalia. (2016). High Emotional Intelligence: Family Psychosocial Factors. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 217. 609-617. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.02.066.
- Lupu, Valentin. (2019). A Study of the Family Structure in Relation to Emotional Intelligence of High School Students. *International conference KNOWLEDGE-BASED ORGANIZATION*. 25. 269-275. 10.2478/kbo-2019-0093.
- Martinez-Pons, Maunel. (1998). Parental Inducement of Emotional Intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*. 18. 1-1. 10.2190/U2LJ-3B8U-M9MG-DMJG.
- Mayer, John D (2008). "Human Abilities: Emotional Intelligence". *Annual Review of Psychology*. 59: 507–536. doi:10.1146/annurev.psych.59.103006.093646. PMID 17937602. Archived from the original on 2015-12-22.
- Ministry of Home Affairs – Social Studies Division. (1991). *Census of India (Occasional paper no. 1)*. New Delhi, India: Author.
- Morand, David. (1999). Family size and intelligence revisited: the role of emotional intelligence.. *Psychological reports*. 84. 643-9. 10.2466/PR0.84.2.643-649.

- Naghavi, Fataneh and Redzuan, Ma'rof (2012) *An empirical research: the relationship between family functioning and early adolescent's emotional intelligence*. Journal of American Science, 8 (5). pp. 580-584. ISSN 1545-1003.
- Naghavi, Fataneh & Redzuan, Ma'rof. (2020). The Moderating Role of Family Ecological Factors (Family Size) on the Relationships between Family Environment and Emotional Intelligence.
- Oelze, P. (2018), There Are 6 Different Family Types And Each One Has A Unique Family Dynamic. Retrieved from <https://www.betterhelp.com/advice/family/there-are-6-different-family-types-and-each-one-has-a-unique-family-dynamic/>
- Ozabaci, N. (2006). *Emotional Intelligence and Family Environment*, Turkey; Osmangazi.
- Sharma, Neha & Kr, Sudha. (2015). A study of relationship of Emotional Intelligence and Family Climate of adolescents at secondary level.
- Singh, Ritu & Pant, Kusha & Laitonjam, Valentina. (2014). Impact Analysis: Family Structure on Social and Emotional Maturity of Adolescents. *Anthropologist*. 17. 359-365. 10.1080/09720073.2014.11891445.
- Sloan, Mary. (2020). Emotional Intelligence of Adults Raised in Different Family Structures. 10.13140/RG.2.2.10052.45441.
- Szcześniak, Małgorzata & Tułeczka, Maria. (2020). Family Functioning and Life Satisfaction: The Mediatory Role of Emotional Intelligence. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*. Volume 13. 223-232. 10.2147/PRBM.S24089